

Review Paper

Herbal Drug Ingredient Used as (CRDDS) Controlled Released Drug Delivery System for the Treatment of Tuberculosis

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) is known as a significant global health challenge for humans, earlier it was managed through a multi-drug regimen that has drawbacks like frequent dosing and poor patient adherence, which leads to drug resistance. CRDDS gives a promising strategy to tackle these limitations by maintaining consistency of drug levels in the blood over an extended period of time and this eventually helps in reducing dosing frequency. This review shows the application of controlled-release drug delivery system, mainly matrix systems using polymers like HPMC for anti-tubercular drugs. It shows the potential of integrating herbal ingredients which is known for its anti-TB properties, such as *Tinospora cordifolia* (Giloy), into these advanced delivery systems. Whereas CR formulations offer advantages like improved patient compliance and decreases side effects, most challenging part is the costing. The article concludes that the further researches and clinical validation are important to fully harness the potential of herbal based CRDDS for managing TB.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis is mainly caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* bacteria. This is a communicable disease that mainly affects the lungs. World Tuberculosis Day is on March 24th to raise public awareness for precautions. According to WHO, tuberculosis was responsible for an approximately 6 million new cases and 1.25 million deaths globally in 2023. The first-line treatment of TB involves a multi-drug regimen is.e combination of

4 drugs like Isoniazid, Rifampin, Pyrazinamide, and Ethambutol. IN THIS regimen TB patients has to intake multiple pills daily for 6-9 months, whivh leads to high pill burden and frequent dosing, the results in non-adherence.

Controlled-Release (CR) drug delivery systems are designed to maintain a constant level of a drug in the blood and tissues for a prolonged duration and give therapeutic effect. This will simplify the simplifying the dosage schedule.

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AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim: To develop a Herbal drug used as crdds for treatment of tuberculosis.

Objectives:

- To examine different technology used in formulating CR tablets for anti-TB drugs.
- To discuss all selection of required excipients, polymers, and their role in making drug release.
- To investigate a potential of incorporating herbal ingredients like *Tinospora cordifolia* in CRDDS.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of existing literature that indicates the Immediate-Release (IR) of anti-TB drugs which have short half-lives, where multiple daily dosing is necessary. The administration of high frequency dose often leads to poor patient adherence, especially in resource-limited settings, which leads to treatment failure and the emergency of drug-resistant TB strains.

CR formulations give a viable solution by giving stable drug levels for a longer period of time, therefore reduces the dosing frequency, by minimizing the peaks, drug concentration. CR systems can improve therapeutic effects and decrease dose-related side effects.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of making this controlled-release tablets for TB is to mark the critical issue of patient's non-adherence. By changing from a multi-dose daily regimen to a single daily dosage form, these formulations help the patient to remember to take medicine and also helps in treatment process. This simplified approach can lead to:

- High cure rates.
- Less treatment failure.
- Will decrease risk of developing drug-resistant TB strains

METHODOLOGY

This review article was compiled through a systematic analysis of existing scientific research papers, review articles, and pharmacopoeial standards. The main databases and resources like Google Scholar, and the Indian Pharmacopoeia was consulted. The focus was on collecting all the useful information for CRDDS, their methods of formulation, parameters of evaluation and the pharmacological way of using *Tinospora cordifolia* for the treatment of TB.

ABOUT THE KEY HERBAL INGREDIENT: TINOSPORA CORDIFOLIA

Scientific Name: *Tinospora cordifolia*

Family: Menispermaceae

Biological Source: This medicinal parts includes the stem, roots, and the whole plant.

Common Names:

- Sanskrit: Guduchi, Amrita;
- Hindi: Giloy, Guruch;
- English: Heart-leaved moonseed.

Uses:

- *Tinospora cordifolia* is famous in traditional medicine for its immunomodulatory, reducing fever, and antihepatotoxic properties.
- Its majorly play role in aid of immunity of the Patient for helper therapy in managing TB.

MECHANISM OF CONTROLLED-RELEASE DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

CR tablets or capsules work through various technological way.

Matrix System : The drug is dissolved uniformly into a polymer matrix like HPMC. When the polymer hydrates and dissolves slowly the drug is released gradually.

Reservoir Systems: The drug (core) is surrounded by polymer membrane which helps in controlling the flow rate. The drug then diffuses through this membrane at a predetermined rate.

Osmotic Systems: These systems use osmotic pressure to push the drug out from a small delivery orifice(hole) made in the tablet.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF CRDDS

Advantages:

- Increase Patient Compliance: Decreased dosing frequency increases the adherence.
- Lower Side Effects: This avoids high peak plasma concentrations, and then minimizes the toxicity.
- Sustained Therapeutic Effect: Maintains drug levels in the therapeutic window for longer period of time.

Disadvantages:

- Risk of Dose Dumping: A doubtful or wrong formulation may lead to sudden release of the entire dose
- Delayed Onset of Action: It is not suitable for immediate relief conditions.
- Higher Cost and Manufacturing: Production involves Proper technology and this is very much expensive than conventional tablets.

EVALUATION AND FORMULATION OF CONTROL RELEASED TABLETS

Formulation Process:

1. Sieve and Blend process : API, polymers like HPMC diluents, required excipients are firstly sieved and then blended for all uniform ingredients.
2. Granulation process: Wet granulation or dry granulation both may be used for better flow, the compression of blend.
3. Lubricating substances: A lubricant is mainly used for preventing sticking of drug during the process of compression.
4. Compressing: The blend is compressed into order to get tablet with the help of a tablet press.
5. Covering or coating: A coating is for firmness, masking of bitter taste of tablets, & decorating purposes. These process is optional.

Evaluation Tests:

1. Physical Characterization: Hardnes, friability, wt variation, and thickness of tablets
2. Drug Content Uniformity: It ensures that each tablet consist of the correct drug dose.
3. In-vitro Dissolution Studies: It conducted in simulated gastrointestinal fluids to see the drug release rate over time (over 24 hours).
4. Stability Studies: This helps to determine the shelf-life that comes under various temperature and humidity condition.
5. In-vivo Pharmacokinetic Studies: It helps to confirm sustained drug release and also helps to know the absorption of drug in a biological system.

OBSERVATION AND DISCUSSION

Pre-clinical and the clinical study on Control Released tablets for Tuberculosis has shown significant promises. The matrix- system employs hydrophilic polymer like HPMC which

has demonstrated sustained drug release over 24 hours successfully. The polymers concentration is a major difficult factor; concentration of higher polymer generally shows result in a slower drug release rate. These Controlled Release formulations Maintains drug concentrations in the therapeutic window for extended period of time, which may decrease side effects related to dose and sub-therapeutic levels that may lead to resistance will be prevented.

CONCLUSION

Controlled-release tablets represent a modification and improvement in TB therapy. By directly focusing on the problem of patient non-adherence, these formulations have the capability to improve treatment outcomes, decrease the incidence of treatment failure. Although it is challenging in large-scale manufacturing process and regulatory approval remain, ongoing research and development strongly supports the potential of CRDDS, especially those making it more effective, patient-friendly, and sustainable.

FUTURE SCOPES:

The future scope of herbal based tablets used as CRDDS are as follows:

1. Enhancement of drug resistance: By Making a systems which can deliver multiple drugs more excellently.
2. Better Adherence and less Duration: It will help in in longer acting formulations which may further shortens the duration of treatment of TB.
3. Unwanted Secondary effects: It may give protective properties of herbs like *Tinospora cordifolia* to reduce down liver toxicity.

4. Futuristic Technology: It may help in survey nano science, and additive manufacturing for more accurate and effective drug delivery.

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